

Synthesis and Reactions of some Chalcones containing a $-\text{CF}_3$ Group

Y. K. SRIVASTAVA, SUDHA SUKHWAL, ANJANA ASHAWA and B. L. VERMA*

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 001

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The chalcones are natural biocides¹ and are well known intermediates in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds exhibiting various biological activities². The introduction of hydroxyl and halogen substituents in the benzenoid part of α,β -unsaturated ketones has been reported³ to appreciably increase the biological activity. The CF_3 group is one of the most lipophilic substituent⁴ and it brings about changes in the biological activities of organic compounds⁵. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and its derivatives have been investigated for their antitumour and antitubercular activities. Pyrazolines⁶ and isoxazolines⁷ are known to possess various antimicrobial activities. The effectiveness of the flavonoids towards various pharmacological screenings promoted us to synthesise few of these systems and some isoxazolines and pyrazolines having a $-\text{CF}_3$ substituent.

o-Hydroxychalcones (1) were synthesised by condens-

ing appropriate *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with 3- or 4-trifluoromethylbenzaldehyde in presence of concentrated aqueous alkali under N_2 atmosphere. The chalcones showed absorption peaks for carbonyl ($1640\text{--}1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$), aromatic and *trans*-ethylenic systems beside other absorptions. They were characterised by preparing their α,β -dibromoderivatives (2). The chalcones were converted by refluxing their alcoholic solution in acidic medium to the corresponding flavanones (3) which exhibited ν_{CO} at $1690\text{--}1680\text{ cm}^{-1}$. ^1H nmr spectrum of 3d exhibited a triplet at δ 5.55 (1H at C-2) and a doublet at δ 2.9–3.1 (1H at C-3). The chalcones on treatment with methanolic solution of alkali and H_2O_2 (30%) at 0° gave the flavonols (4) which exhibited ν_{OH} at 3260 cm^{-1} and ν_{CO} at 1630 cm^{-1} . The reaction of the chalcones (1) with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in refluxing pyridine gave 3,5-diaryl- Δ^2 -isoxazolines (5) and the reaction of isonicotinic acid hydrazide with chalcones and flavanones afforded the corresponding N^1 -isonicotinoyl-3,5-diaryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines (6). Ir spectra of 5 and 6 revealed the presence of OH stretching and C=N vibrational peaks.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. The purity and homogeneity of the compounds were checked by tlc using silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer.

Isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) was prepared by the reported method⁸. Chalcones⁹ (1a-f), α,β -dibromo-chalcones⁹ (2a-f), flavanones (3a-f), flavonols¹⁰ (4a-f), 3,5-diaryl- Δ^2 -isoxazolines¹¹ (5a-f) and N^1 -isonicotinoyl-3,5-diaryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolines¹² (6a-f) were prepared according to known procedures.

Chalcones (1): A mixture of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 mol) and appropriate trifluoromethyl benzaldehyde (0.12 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) in aqueous NaOH (50%; 10 ml) was stirred under N_2 -atmosphere, kept at room temperature for 4 h and then decomposed with dilute HCl (10%) in cold condition. The separated solid was washed free of acid and crystallised from ethanol as yellow or orange yellow crystals (yields 45–78%): **1a**, m.p. 94° ; **b**, 116° ; **c**, 129° ; **d**, 132° ; **e**, 114° ; **f**, 126° .

α,β -Dibromo-chalcones (2): To 2'-hydroxychalcone (0.1 mol) suspended in acetic acid (15.0 ml) was added a solution of bromine in acetic acid (25% w/v, 6.4 ml) and stirred to get a clear solution after 15 min. The resulting

- a; R = R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-CF₃
b; R = CH₃; R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-CF₃
c; R = Cl; R₁ = H; R₂ = 4-CF₃
d; R = R₁ = Cl; R₂ = 4-CF₃
e; R = Cl; R₁ = H; R₂ = 3-CF₃
f; R = R₁ = Cl; R₂ = 3-CF₃

yellow crystals were washed with acetic acid (2 × 10 ml) and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 58–80%) : **2a**, m.p. 182°; **b**, 162°; **c**, 189°; **d**, 177°; **e**, 128°; **f**, 152°.

Flavanones (3) : To 2'-hydroxychalcone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50.0 ml), concentrated H₂SO₄ (8.0 ml) was added slowly and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled to room temperature and left overnight. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals. Similarly, other compounds were prepared (yields 56–85%) : **3a**, m.p. 88°; **b**, 86°; **c**, 98°; **d**, 106°; **e**, 94°; **f**, 142°.

Flavonols (4) : 2'-Hydroxychalcone (0.01 mol) was added to a mixture of methanol (20 ml) and aqueous NaOH (20%; 10 ml). The mixture was kept at 0° in ice, H₂O₂ (30%; 4 ml) added and was stirred for 2 h in ice and for 3 h at room temperature. The resulting yellow semisolid liquid was acidified with ice-cold acetic acid and kept overnight. The separated solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals. Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 63–87%) : **4a**, m.p. 181°; **b**, 214°; **c**, 230°; **d**, 218°; **e**, 171°; **f**, 189°.

3,5-Diaryl-Δ²-isoxazolines (5) : A mixture of 2'-hydroxychalcone (0.01 mol) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol) in pyridine was refluxed for 4–5 h. The cooled mixture was then acidified with dilute AcOH and the semisolid obtained was triturated with EtOH. Crystallisation from benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) afforded colourless crystals. Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 46–63%) : **5a**, m.p. 181°; **b**, 241°; **c**, 180°; **d**, 171°; **e**, 147°; **f**, 186°.

N¹-Isonicotinoyl-3,5-diphenyl-Δ²-pyrazolines (6) : A mixture of 2'-hydroxychalcone or flavanone (0.01 mol) in EtOH (60 ml) and isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.012 mol) was refluxed for 12–18 h, then cooled to room temperature and the separated solid was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) as colourless crystals. Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 40–55%) : **6a**, m.p. 231°; **b**, 242°; **c**, 251°; **d**, 214°; **e**, 221°; **f**, 217°.

Biological screening : Compounds **1**, **2** and **5** were

screened for their antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. albus*, *S. boydii* and *P. morgani*. Compounds **1** and **2** were found to be inactive. However, compounds **5c** and **5d** were found active against *S. aureus* at a concentration of 0.05 mg ml⁻¹. Inactivity of **5e** and **5f** indicates that change of the position of -CF₃ group from *para* to *meta* results in the loss of activity. Compounds **6a-f** were tested against *M. tuberculosis* H 37 Rv for their antitubercular activity and none of them was found to be active.

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